

Grant Agreement No: 101004761

AIDAInnova

Advancement and Innovation for Detectors at Accelerators
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures project AIDAINNOVA

DELIVERABLE REPORT

LARGE SCALE PIXEL ANODE

DELIVERABLE: D9.1

Document identifier:	AIDAInnova_D9.1
Due date of deliverable:	End of Month 44 (November 2024)
Report release date:	15/03/2025
Work package:	WP9: Cryogenic Neutrino Detectors
Lead beneficiary:	UNIMAN
Document status:	Final

Abstract:

The goal of WP9 is to develop a novel pixel readout for large scale liquid argon TPCs targeting neutrino detection. Compared to the wire-based readout currently used in single-phase liquid-argon detectors, pixelated readout will reduce reconstruction ambiguities through the direct readout of 3D space points compared to the 2D projections used in current detectors and facilitate the production of readout elements compared to the DUNE large anode wire plane assemblies (APAs). A pixel pattern can be designed in a way that maximises the 3D reconstruction efficiency. Pixel PCB board designs for large scale anode planes using pixel tiles need to fulfil the tight requirement for mechanical and electrical tolerances defined by large scale cryogenic neutrino detectors. The outcome of this deliverable is the design of an optimised pixel tile pattern for the DUNE far detector, and the design and the construction of a prototype for large scale tile-based anode plane. The main applications are the DUNE far detector and the DUNE near detector, ArgonCube.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2025

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

The Advancement and Innovation for Detectors at Accelerators (AIDAinnova) project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101004761. AIDAinnova began in April 2021 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	Stefan Söldner-Rembold, Ines Gil Botella, Michele Weber, Francesco Terranova, Saba Parsa, Anyssa Navrer-Agasson, Daniele Guffanti	LHEP, CIEMAT, Milano-Bicocca, Imperial, Manchester.	13/02/2025
Edited by	A. Szelc	UEDIN	20/02/2025
Reviewed by	Paolo Giacomelli [Scientific coordinator]	INFN	10/03/2025
Approved by	Paolo Giacomelli [Scientific coordinator] Steering Committee		15/03/2025

TABLE OF CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION	4
PIXEL-ANODE PROTOYPES	4
1.1. THE SOLAR V1 PROTOTYPE	4
1.2. SOLAR V2.....	5
1.3. INTEGRATED LIGHT AND CHARGE SENSOR PIXEL ANODE FOR FUTURE APPLICATIONS	6
CONCLUSIONS AND DUNE PHASE II.....	7
REFERENCES	8

Executive summary

This deliverable report describes the design and operation of two prototypes using the integrated charge-light pixel design for a read-out anode proposed by the SoLAr collaboration. The results of the first prototype have been published, and the publication of the result of the second prototype, using a larger anode pixel tile is currently in preparation. The combined light-charge collection was demonstrated using small-size prototypes. The prototypes were operated successfully and have demonstrated that the principle of combining charge and light readout is possible. Future opportunities to test the technology will be provided by the ProtoDUNE detectors on CERN's neutrino platform.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, the liquid-argon time projection chamber (LArTPC) technology has undergone significant advancements, paving the way for the next generation of large-scale, long-baseline neutrino experiments like DUNE. At the heart of these developments is the SoLAr detector concept, which features new charge/light readout tiles with innovative pixel geometry and configurations. SoLAr aims to enhance the sensitivity of detectors in the MeV energy range, with the goal of observing solar neutrinos and potentially supernova neutrinos. While the primary focus of this work package is on charge readout, the core concept integrates both charge and light readout into a single plane. This plane combines pixel pads for charge collection with VUV silicon photomultipliers (SiPMs) for the direct detection of liquid-argon scintillation light.

Key challenges include achieving low energy thresholds with excellent energy resolution, as well as effective background rejection using pulse shape discrimination. The SoLAr concept represents a promising technology option for the DUNE fourth far-detector module, potentially acting as a next-generation multi-purpose neutrino observatory for energies ranging from the MeV to the GeV scale. A staged prototyping program has been implemented to progressively validate the detector concept. In October 2022 and July 2023, small-scale SoLAr prototypes were built and tested in LAr at Bern University. Building on the lessons learned from these tests, the SOLAIRE proposal was developed to establish a larger test facility at the Boulby Underground Laboratory. Future tests are planned at CERN as part of upcoming ProtoDUNE runs, where SoLAr will be integrated with other charge and light readout technologies.

PIXEL-ANODE PROTOYPES

1.1. THE SOLAR V1 PROTOTYPE

In 2022, we operated for the first time a liquid-argon TPC with a new readout concept (SoLAr), integrating charge and light sensors on the same surface, to perform native 3D reconstruction of an event. In a publication [1], we presented the design of a first small demonstrator, referred to as SoLAr Prototype-v1, which used an integrated dual-pixel readout of light and charge pixels, based on a distributed arrangement of VUV SiPMs on the anode plane. The schematic design of this integrated cell is shown in Figure 1 and a photograph of the empty TPC in Figure 2 (left). The Prototype-v1 was operated in October 2022 at the University of Bern and collected cosmic-ray muon tracks. The student funded through the EU AIDAInnova project performed the electric field simulations for the prototype, participated in the data taking and the data analysis.

We showed unambiguous correlations between the light and charge information from these cosmic-ray tracks. An event display is shown in Figure 2 (right). We also showed that the charge collection of the ionization electrons corresponds to a Landau-Gaussian distribution, demonstrating that this detector has the potential to perform calorimetric measurements despite the interleaved SiPMs. The light collection on the SiPM is efficient and independent on the ground offset voltage of the SiPM bias, necessary to tune the drift field to guide the ionization electrons to the charge pads.

Figure 1: Schematic of a single cell design (left) within the sensitive area of the LArTPC. Charge-collecting pixels are located directly next to the pin of each SiPM; the complete v1 prototype tile with all 16 cells (right) [1].

The results from this first prototype opened the path for the design of detectors using the integrated light-charge pixel concept to detect interactions from GeV to the MeV energy scale in very large (multi-kiloton) mass detectors, suitable e.g. for solar neutrino measurements. The results from the first prototype informed the design of the prototype v2 that was scaled in size and used to characterize and optimize the capability of the SoLAr concept for LArTPCs to detect neutrino signals at the MeV-scale.

Figure 2: (left) Interior of the SoLAr-v1 TPC time projection chamber with the cathode plate, the side panels for E-field shaping and the readout anode plane containing the SiPMs and charge pixels. (right) A cosmic-ray event recorded by the prototype shown from the anode view in the xy plane and as zy view, where z is the drift direction [1].

1.2. SOLAR V2

The SoLAr prototype-v2 was operated at LHEP Bern in July 2023, again with contribution from the participating institutions. A publication is in preparation. Prototype-V2 operated a larger (30 x 30 cm²) tile with a single multilayer PCB, 20 LArPix chips and 64 VUV SiPMs. This prototype collected data using a ⁶⁰Co source in addition to cosmic muon runs. The track reconstruction in SoLAr v2 was based on a well-established analysis tools to cluster, then fit, hits in the 3D space. Some chips

malfunctioned during the data acquisition, causing several pixels to be unresponsive. Together, these create holes on the anode plane, leading to "dead areas" (see Figure 3 left).

Figure 3: (left) Heat map showing the hit count in each pixel. The dead areas can be seen clearly as empty bins. (right) 2D distribution of the total event light as a function of the collected charge for single track events.

The SoLAR V2 run recorded cosmic muon events, out of which one is depicted in the event display in Figure 4 with both charge and light signal. The correlation between charge and light is shown in Figure 3 (right). A quantitative analysis of the light-charge correlation, the specific energy loss, dQ/dx , the electron lifetime, and other performance parameters in the TPC is currently being finalized, with the student funded through this project as primary analyser. A publication is imminent.

Figure 4: Cosmic muon event collected by the SoLAR V2 prototype.

1.3. INTEGRATED LIGHT AND CHARGE SENSOR PIXEL ANODE FOR FUTURE APPLICATIONS

The extensive experience with the first two prototypes informed the design of integrated charge and light sensors, which was presented as part of the SOLAIRE proposal submitted to STFC for a common detector concept for SoLAR and the Darkside collaboration. As the SOLAIRE project was not funded, the next step is to test the sensors as part of a future ProtoDUNE run at CERN, under the umbrella of the DUNE Phase II organization. The SoLAR concept was also presented as part of the DUNE Phase II White Paper that was recently published [2].

The integrated light-and-charge sensor boards proposed for SOLAIRE would cover 3 m² of the SOLAIRE anode. Each board would be comprising 6084 charge-readout pixels of 1 mm² spaced by 3.14 mm², placed in a grid of 78×78 combined with 169 6×6 mm² Hamamatsu VUV sensitive SiPMs placed in a grid of 13×13 resulting in a board size of 24.8×24.8 cm². See Figure 5 for a layout of the board. This design provides a 10% photodetector coverage of the anode resulting in an estimated 3% photon detection efficiency assuming a 30% quantum efficiency of the SiPMs. Each board would use 96 Q-Pix/LArPix chips to readout the charge signal and 3 LightPix chips to readout the light signals from the boards. This would be the largest pixel-anode built to date and the design is scalable to a full-size DUNE detector.

Figure 5: Design of the all-silicon integrated tile.

CONCLUSIONS AND DUNE PHASE II

The SoLAR technology is based on the concept of a monolithic, light-charge, pixel-based readout to achieve a low energy threshold with excellent energy resolution of about 7% at few-MeV neutrino energies and background rejection through pulse-shape discrimination. In the SoLAR preparatory phase (2021-2024), funded by EU-AIDAInnova, combined light-charge collection was demonstrated using small-size prototypes. The prototypes were operated successfully and have demonstrated that the principle of combining charge and light readout is possible. Simulations accounting for light propagation effects have shown that a 7% energy resolution can be achieved at typical solar neutrino energies (5--20~MeV) and using the scintillation signal only by replacing anode planes with a pixelated readout integrating a light-sensitive area covering about 10% of the surface. This system would enhance the amount of collected light by a factor of five compared with DUNE Phase I, reducing the frequency at which low-energy background gets incorrectly reconstructed to the (higher) energy region of interest of the signal.

The combination of shielding and a 7% energy resolution gives access to the 5-10 MeV region, where most of the 8B neutrinos reside, by greatly reducing the dominant background from neutrons and 42-K. Light collection outside the anode would be ensured by X-Arapuca tiles, for a total coverage of 8-10%. The latter provide the appropriate light yield without resorting to xenon doping, thus preserving the pulse-shape discrimination power of liquid argon. Pulse-shape discrimination is further enhanced with respect to any existing LArTPC by the unique performance of the tile design and the increase of collected light.

We currently focus on the publication of the results of the version 2 prototype and on developing a concept for the validation of the technology in a future ProtoDUNE Run.

REFERENCES

JOURNAL ARTICLES:

[1] N. Anfimov, et al., (SoLAr collaboration), First Demonstration of a Combined Light and Charge Pixel Readout on the Anode Plane of a LArTPC, *Journal of Instrumentation*, **19** P11010

[2] A. Abed Abud et al (DUNE Collaboration), DUNE Phase II: Scientific Opportunities, Detector Concepts, Technological Solutions, *ePrint*, arxiv:2408.12725

CONFERENCE PAPERS:

[3] J. Kunzmann et al. (SoLAr collaboration), SoLAr: a novel LAr TPC to detect MeV neutrinos, 2024, *Journal of Instrumentation*, **19** C02075, DOI 10.1088/1748-0221/19/02/C02075

CONFERENCE PRESENTATIONS

R. Diurba, “Prototyping the SoLAr LArTPC Technology for Detecting MeV-Scale Neutrinos”, 42nd International Conference on High Energy Physics (ICHEP), Prague, July 20 2024

D. Guffanti, “SoLAr: a novel approach to multipurpose LArTPCs for neutrino physics”, Conference on Science at the Sanford Underground Research Facility (CoSSURF), Rapid City, May 14 2024

G. Ruiz Ferreira, “SoLAr: A novel technology for solar neutrino detection”, IOP Joint APP, HEPP and NP Annual Conference 2024, Liverpool, 10 April 2024

A. Gauch, “Prototyping the SoLAr dual readout LAr TPC to enable solar neutrino detection program”, 29th International Workshop on Neutrino Telescopes (NuTel2023), Venice, October 24 2023

J. Kunzmann, “SoLAr: A future LAr TPC to detect MeV-scale neutrinos”, 16th Topical Seminar on Innovative particle and radiation detectors (IPRD23), Siena, September 27 2023

J. Bürgi, “An overview of SoLAr, a novel approach to LArTPCs in the MeV range”, LIDINE 2023: Light Detection In Noble Elements, Madrid, September 20 2023

S. Parsa, “SoLAr detector small scale prototype”, Technology & Instrumentation in Particle Physics (TIPP23), Cape Town, September 6 2023

S. Parsa, “Solar neutrinos in Liquid Argon (SoLAr)”, 18th International Conference on Topics in Astroparticle and Underground Physics (TAUP23), Wien, August 28 2023

D. Guffanti, “The SoLAr proposal: Project status and synergies with APEX”, DUNE-FD3 Mini-Workshop, Stony Brook, June 28 2023

A. Navrer-Agasson, “Update on SoLAr and Pixel R&D”, AIDAInnova 2nd annual meeting, Valencia, April 26 2023

A. Navrer-Agasson, “The SoLAr concept: LArTPCs for solar neutrino studies”, IOP-HEPP, April 2-5 2023

S. Parsa, “4D LArTPCs: combined charge and light readout”, DUNE Module of Opportunity Workshop, Valencia, November 4 2022

A. Navrer-Agasson, “The SoLAr concept”, DUNE Module of Opportunity Workshop, Valencia, November 3 2022

D. Guffanti, “SoLAr: LArTPCs in the next decade of solar neutrino physics”, 21st International Workshop on Next Generation Nucleon Decay and Neutrino Detectors (NNN22), Hida, September 29 2022

CONFERENCE POSTERS:

L. Calivers, “Progress in SoLAr Towards Reconstructing MeV-scale Neutrinos”, 31st International Conference on Neutrino Physics and Astrophysics, Milan, 2024 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13124352

Guilherme Ruiz Ferreira. (2024). “SoLAr: A novel technology for solar neutrino detection”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11447758>

THESES:

Guilherme Ruiz Ferreira, University of Manchester, *in Preparation*.